

MICRO-MACRO DESIGN OF THERMAL STRESSES OF CERAMIC-METAL GRADIENT COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The present study is concerned with the design of a newly developed composite material-functionally gradient composite material^[1]. A three-phase mean-field micromechanical model is applied to analyze the thermomechanical properties of the ceramic-metal gradient composite material. The porosities in the composite interlayers are assumed to vary parabolically. Based on a finite element simulated for the thermal stresses generated in the material fabrication, a design method for constituent distribution in the FGM interlayers is proposed. According to the design results for the constituent distribution, a MgO/Ni FGM with thermal stress relaxation has been obtained.

Keywords: micro-macro design, functionally gradient composite material, thermal stress

INTRODUCTION

Functionally gradient composite materials (FGM) are based on a new concept of material design in which material properties are optimized for use in real environment which usually include severe temperature conditions. The material is characterized by continuous variation of the microstructure in one or several directions. A ceramic-metal FGM plate, for example, has a characteristic microstructural transition with ceramic-metal mixing ratio varying from a dispersive microstructure with ceramic particles in metal matrix to an alternative dispersive one with metal particles in ceramic matrix, through the formation of network structures in the intermediate composition range with various connectivities. Therefore the material shows a consecutive change along thickness directions, showing ceramic properties in its ceramic side and metal properties in its metal side, but in the interlayers between the two sides, the properties experience a continuous transition through the plate thickness. At the same time, as the constituents of FGM contain voids, the distribution of porosity has an influence on the material properties of FGM. Since material properties, such as mechanical properties, are strongly dependent on the microstructures of the material, it is highly important to evaluate the microstructural transition in order to control the material properties and to improve FGM performance. For the design of FGM, thermomechanical properties (thermal expansion coefficient, Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio in interlayers) optimized by controlling the distribution profiles of composition and microstructure as well as are voids in the materials. For this purpose, We use a three-phase mean-field micromechanical model to analyze the thermomechanical properties of the ce-

ramic—metal gradient composite material. Then, based on a finite element simulation for the thermal stress generated in the material fabrication, the design method for the constituent distribution in the FGM interlayers is proposed. According to the design results for the constituent distribution, a MgO/Ni FGM with thermal stress relaxation has been obtained.

ANALYSIS MODEL OF CERAMIC—METAL FGM

The model for the thermal stress calculation of ceramic—metal FGM takes a fabricated MgO/Ni stepwise FGM sample. The geometry of the sample is a disk—shaped plate with 6mm in thickness, 30mm in diameter and 11 gradient layers. The calculation condition for the thermal load is the same as the fabrication one (the sample is sintered at 1300°C and cooled down to room temperature). The top side is a metal layer, the bottom side is a ceramic layer. The compositional distribution in the FGM interlayers is assumed to take a form of $c = (\frac{x}{d})^{p(2)}$, where c is the compositional distribution (the volume fraction of MgO), d is the distance in the gradient interlayer, x is the layer location coordinate measured from the Ni side, and p is the distribution exponent. The porosities in interlayers assume changing according to a parabola⁽³⁾:

$$c_2 = Ax(1 - x) \quad (1)$$

where c_2 is the fractional volume of voids, A is the porosity in $\frac{d}{2}$. The fractional volumes of ceramic phase c_0 and metal phase c_1 and voids c_2 satisfy the following equation

$$c_0 + c_1 + c_2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

Then, the fractional volumes of the constituents ceramic and metal can be expressed as functions of c and an independent distribution c_0 , as follows:

$$c_0 = (1 - c_2)c \quad (3)$$

$$c_1 = (1 - c_2)(1 - c) \quad (4)$$

Due to the axisymmetric problem, the axisymmetric finite element formula with axisymmetric quadrilateral elements is employed in the present calculation. By using the cylindrical coordinate system and taking the Z —axis along the thickness of the plate, the half of the r — z plane is considered.

MICROMECHANICAL PREDICTION FOR MATERIAL PROPERTIES

In order to calculate the thermal stress distribution in the FGM, effective thermomechanical properties for interlayers are required. There are several ways implemented in the system for estimating the effective material properties of the interlayers. Based on Esheby's equivalent inclusion method and Mori—Tanaka's mean—field theory, Wakashima et al⁽⁴⁾ derived a micromechanical formula for two—phases composites. G. J. Weng⁽⁵⁾ developed a mean—field micromechanical theory for a general multiphase composites and gave explicit formulas for three—phase composites. As compared with the experimental data of several FGM systems, the three—phase mean—field theory provides reasonably accurate estimates for the effective material properties⁽⁶⁾. The three—phase mean—field theory expression is:

$$k = k_0 + k_0 \frac{a}{1 - h_0 a} \quad u = u_0 + u_0 \frac{b}{1 - h_1 b}$$

$$\alpha = \sum \frac{c_r k_r \alpha_r}{h_2 [k_0 + h_0 (k_r - k_0)]} \quad (5)$$

where:

$$h_0 = \frac{3k_0}{3k_0 + 4\mu_0} \quad h_1 = \frac{6}{5} \frac{k_0 + 2\mu_0}{3k_0 + 4\mu_0} \quad h_2 = 1 + a(1 - h_0)$$

$$a = \sum \frac{c_r(k_r - k_0)}{h_0(k_r - k_0) + k_0} \quad b = \sum \frac{c_r(\mu_r - \mu_0)}{h_1(\mu_r - \mu_0) + \mu_0}$$

where k , u and α are the effective bulk modulus, shear modulus and thermal expansion coefficient of the composite and k_r , u_r , α_r are the corresponding constants of r -phase, specially, 0 -phase express the matrix phase.

For the present MgO/Ni system, the Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and thermal expansion coefficients are⁽⁷⁾:

MgO	E=103.7GPa,	$\nu=0.160$	$\alpha=12.78 \times 10^{-6} \quad l/k,$
Ni	E=145.5GPa,	$\nu=0.350,$	$\alpha=15.10 \times 10^{-6} \quad l/k,$
voids	E=0.0GPa,	$\nu=0.0$	$\alpha=0.0.$

THERMAL STRESS ANALYSIS OF CERAMIC—METAL FGM

For various distribution exponent p values assumed, the thermal stresses of the FGM plate are calculated and the results are given in Figure 1—Figure 4. The MgO/Ni directly bonded material(NFGM), with the same configuration as the FGM and without the interlayers, is analyzed under the same calculation conditions for comparison.

The calculation results show that the radial stress is the largest among the thermal stress components. The shear stress is small compared with the radial and axial stresses and can be ignored in the present discussion. The maximum values for both the radial and circumferential stresses are about the same. A stress distribution quite similar to that for the radial has also been obtained for the circumferential stress. Therefore the main fracture stress is the radial stress in the present case. The fracture analysis for the FGM samples should be based on the consideration for the radial stress.

Form the thermal stress analysis, it is indicated that with the exponent p values ranging from 0.4 to 2.0 the thermal stresses in any of the FGM plates are relaxed with respect to the directly bonded material(NFGM). At $p=0.4$ and $c_2=0\%$, for instance, the maximum radial tensile stress σ_{rr} is 49.3MPa, which is reduced 82.76% compared with the corresponding value in the bonded material. In the case of $p=1.0$ and $c_2=0\%$, the maximum radial tensile stress σ_{rr} relaxation in the FGM plate arrives at 91.15%.

From Figures 1—4, it is indicated that with exponent p values ranging from 0.4 to 2.0, we can come to the conclusion that there exists a minimum stress exponent value near $p=1.0$ for both of the radial and axial stresses for the same voids content. The maximum values and locations of radial and axial stresses change with the exponent p . When $p=0.4$ and $c_2=0\%$, the maximum tensile stresses $\sigma_{rr}=49.4\text{MPa}, \sigma_{zz}=12.5\text{MPa}$; the maximum compressive stresses $\sigma_{rr}=-131\text{MPa}, \sigma_{zz}=-58.2\text{MPa}$. The location of the maximum radial tensile stress is at the ceramic rich interlayers, which may yield crack formation at the sample surface, while about 80% of the axial stress in the free edge of the sample is compressive, which is beneficial in increasing the tear strength. When $p=1.0$ and $c_2=0\%$, the maximum tensile stresses $\sigma_{rr}=25.3\text{MPa}, \sigma_{zz}=4.05\text{MPa}$; the maximum compressive stresses $\sigma_{rr}=-42.2\text{MPa}, \sigma_{zz}=-18.2\text{MPa}$. The maximum value of the radial stress at $p=1.0$ decreases by 67.78% than that at $p=0.4$. The maximum value of the axial stress at $p=1.0$ decreases by 68.73% from that at $p=0.4$. At the same time the location of the maximum radial tensile stress at $p=1.0$ moves to the middle of the sample. The thermal stresses at $p=1.0$ are evidently relaxed compared with those at $p=0.4$ for the same voids content.

Figures 1—4 show the influence of the voids on the thermal stresses. In these figures, there are four different porosities; $c_2=0\%, 5\%, 10\%, 15\%$. Compared with the case of $p=1.0$ and $c_2=0\%$, the maximum radial tensile stress is decreased by 7.11%, 13.04%, 12.

65%, for $p=1.0$ and $c_2=5\%, 10\%, 15\%$, the maximum radial compressive stress decreased by 0.95%, 0.72%, 2.6%, the maximum axial tensile stresses decreased by 5.68%, 5.76%, 16.05%, the maximum axial compressive stresses decreased by 6.04%, 5.85%, 17.03%.

CONCLUSION

In order to relax the thermal stresses caused by material fabrication, the compositional profiles of MgO/Ni functionally gradient composite material (FGM) were analysed by FEM. Based on the results, the design method for the constituent distribution in FGM interlayers is proposed as follows:

(1) The thermal stresses in any of the FGM plates are relaxed with respect to the directly bonded material (NFGM).

(2) The main fracture stress is the radial stress in the present case, therefore the fracture analysis for the FGM samples should be based on the consideration for the radial stress.

(3) There exists a minimum stress exponent value near $p=1.0$ for the thermal stresses.

(4) The effect of voids on the thermal stresses is: at $p=1.0$, the radial and axial stresses decrease significantly with the increase of porosity, the voids exert a more significant influence on the maximum tensile radial stress, the effect of voids on the maximum axial stress increases significantly after c_2 reaches 10%.

According to the design result for the constituent distribution, a MgO/Ni FGM with thermal stress relaxation has been obtained.

REFERENCES

1. J. B. Holt and Z. A. Munir. Proc. 2nd Int symp on FGM (FGM'92), Nov. 1—4, 1992, San Francisco, California, to be published by the American Ceramic Society, Inc. (1993).
2. A. Kawasaki and R. Watanabe, Microstructural Designing and Fabrication of Disk Shaped Functionally Gradient Material by Power Metallurgy, J. Japan Soc. Power and Metal, 37 (1990), 253.
3. Y. Obata and N. Noda, Steady Thermal Stresses in a Plate of Functionally Gradient Material, Proc. the 1st Int symp on FGM (FGM'90), pp. 215—221, 1990, Sendai, Japan.
4. K. Wakashima and H. Tsukamoto, Micromechanical Approach to the Thermomechanics of Ceramic—Metal Gradient Materials, Proc. the 1st Int symp on FGM (FGM'90), pp. 19—26, 1990, Sendai, Japan.
5. G. J. Weng, Some Elastic Properties of Reinforced Solids, with Special Reference to Isotropic Ones Containing Spherical Inclusions, Int. J. Engng Sci. Vol. 22, No. 7, pp. 845—856, 1984.
6. P. C. Zhai, C. R. Jiang and Q. J. Zhang, Application of Three—Phase Micro—Mechanical Theories to Ceramic—Metal Functionally Gradient Materials, Proc. 2nd Int symp on FGM (FGM'92), Nov. 1—4, 1992, San Francisco, California, to be published by the American Ceramic Society, Inc. (1993)
7. L. M. Zhang, R. Z. Yuan, Q. J. Zhang and X. F. Tang, Design and Fabrication of A MgO/Ni Functionally Gradient Material, Journal of Materials Synthesis Processing, Vol. 1, No. 3, 1993

Fig. 1 Maximum radial tensile stresses with respect to various compositional exponent values

Fig. 2 Maximum radial compressive stresses with respect to various compositional exponent values

Fig. 3 Maximum axial tensile stresses with respect to various compositional exponent values

Fig. 4 Maximum axial compressive stresses with respect to various compositional exponent values